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Dear Authors,

Einas M.A. Widaa, Mohamed Yahia Shirgawi, Abeer Mohammed Khairy Ahmed, Mohammed
Ismail Adam Saleh, Musa Ibrahim Babiker Hussein, Ebtisam A. Yousef, Manahil A.

Mohammed Ashmaig, A.H. Abdelrahman, Najwa Idris A. Ahmed

E-mail: misaleh@bu.edu.sa

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We are pleased to inform you that your manuscript, **“Quantum–Biophysical Modeling of Light–Tissue Interaction via Schrödinger–Maxwell Coupling and Relativistic Extensions for Photodynamic Therapy,”** has been accepted for publication in Letter in Biomathematics, (E-ISSN: 2373-7867).

We believe this study will contribute valuable insights to the field. If you have any other inquiries, please do not hesitate to reach out.

Best regards,

Editor In Chief

Letter in Biomathematics

For any Query Contact:

editor@lettersinbiomath.org

